

GSA'S CAPABILITIES TO SUPPORT NSEP TELECOMMUNICATIONS

George F. Flynn Jr., and Rose Ann Shelley

General Services Administration

GSA can provide numerous essentially needed, as well as operational services to all NSEP users during peacetime and wartime stress conditions. The Office of FTS2000 manages the program which provides long-distance telecommunications services to government locations throughout the United States, Puerto Rico, Guam, and the U.S. Virgin Islands. The Information Resources Management Service manages consolidated local telecommunications services, the Purchases of Telecommunications Services (POTS) program, the Delegation of Procurement Authority process for agencies to acquire telecommunications services, and the worldwide Federal Secure Telephone Service (FSTS).

The General Services Administration (GSA) manages Governmentwide telecommunications systems that provide both local and long distance services. Service is provided to over two million Federal customers and the number continues to grow. As part of this management responsibility, GSA provides telecommunications services during all types of emergencies and disasters. National Security Emergency Preparedness (NSEP) is a mandated responsibility in GSA's authorities and mission.

GSA's goal is to provide enduring, survivable, and restorable telecommunications, with end-to-end encryption, if required, to Federal agencies in the event of a national emergency. GSA's NSEP telecommunications responsibility is broadly delineated in Executive Order 12472, Assignment of NSEP Telecommunications Functions, signed by President Reagan in April 1984. E. O. 12472, assigns GSA the responsibility "to ensure that federally owned or managed domestic communications facilities and services meet the national security and emergency preparedness requirements of the Federal civilian departments, agencies and entities."

To meet this challenge, GSA provides services through programs managed by the Office of FTS2000 and the Information Resources Management Service. The Office of FTS2000 manages the program which provides long-distance telecommunications services to government locations throughout the United States, Puerto Rico, Guam, and the U.S. Virgin Islands. The Information Resources Management Service manages consolidated local telecommunications services, the Purchase of Telecommunications and Services (POTS) program, the Delegation of Procurement Authority process for agencies to acquire telecommunications services, and the worldwide Federal Secure Telephone Service (FSTS). In recognizing the interrelationship between these programs, GSA's focus is on providing end-to-end NSEP services and features to the Government's NSEP critical users throughout major U.S. cities.

GSA provides numerous essential services to all users during peacetime disasters and emergencies, mobilizations, and wartime stress conditions. As a result, Federal departments and agencies, including the Department of Defense, have the flexibility to choose the level of service and the degree of sophistication, as well as the equipment and technical support that is necessary to accomplish their agency's unique NSEP mission.

FTS2000

FTS2000 is a state-of-the-art, cost effective intercity telecommunications system that utilizes advanced digital telecommunications and fiber optics technology to provide an impressive variety of quality long-distance voice, data and video services.

FTS2000's inherent NSEP capabilities include:

- o Backup Power
- o Backup Control Memory
- o Non-Hierarchical Dynamic Routing
- o Dual Networks

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- o Traffic Overload Protection
- o Operator Assistance
- o Diverse Network Access Routing
- o Multiple Network Switch Homing
- o Dual Networks Access
- o Expedited Service Order Processing
- o Telecommunications Service Priority
- o Assured Service (Priority Que Service)
- o Authorization Codes (Critical Users)
 - On Net
 - Off Net - On Net
 - Off Net - On Net - Off Net
- o 800 Number Service
- o Conferencing (Fixed/Portable)
 - Voice
 - Datacom
 - Compressed
 - Wideband
- o Special Announcements
- o Hotlines
- o Load Control - Trunk Group Denial
- o User Access Restrictions
- o Electronic Mail
- o Automatic Call Routing

CONSOLIDATED LOCAL SERVICE

The GSA consolidated local services program provides telecommunications services and support to Government agencies in local geographic areas, nationwide. GSA consolidated local telecommunications services are an important part of the Federal Government's NSEP support system. The Washington Interagency Telecommunications System (WITS) and the Aggregated Systems Procurement (ASP) are two local service program initiatives that support NSEP objectives.

Consolidated local service's inherent capabilities include:

- o Backup Power
- o Backup Control Memory
- o Load Control
- o Dial Tone Denial
- o Trunk Group Denial
- o Access Restrictions

- o Diverse Physical Routing-User Access
- o Multiple Switch Homing
- o User Access Restrictions
- o Class of Service Marking
 - o Voice
 - o Data
- o Automatic Call Forwarding
- o Call Waiting + Special Announcements
- o Special Tones
- o Special Voice Message
- o Conferencing
 - o Voice
 - o Datacom
- o Special Announcements
- o Dial Tone Transfer
- o Unique Ringing for Selected Calls
- o Call Splitting
- o Call Screening
- o Expedited Order Processing
- o Telecommunications Service Priority

PURCHASE OF TELECOMMUNICATIONS SERVICES (POTS)

POTS is a regional telecommunications services technical assistance program which provides a contracting mechanism that Federal agencies may use to obtain telecommunications equipment and contractor support. This includes telephones and other customer premises equipment, maintenance of new and used equipment, and other services such as installation, removal, repair, and moves of new and used equipment.

POTS contracts provide:

- o Less than 500 line switches
- o Key Sets
- o Voice Customer Station Equipment
- o Datacom Customer Premises Equipment (including modems)
- o Cellular Radio Customer Premises equipment (not including cellular radio service)
- o Video Customer Premises Equipment (Possible Future)
- o Installation and Design Services

- o Consulting Services
- o Expedited Order Processing
- o Expedited Installation Service

SECURITY SERVICES

Security services may be required by some NSEP users to carry out missions that require the controlled dissemination of classified and/or sensitive, unclassified information. GSA's security objective is to provide end user security that is timely; effective; easy to order; and economical.

GSA's security goals are to:

- o Enhance Government's Security Posture
- o Ensure Internal System Security
- o Develop Required Security Services

GSA security services include:

- o System Engineering Design
- o Material Management
- o System Installation and Maintenance
- o Support to Foreign Military Sales
- o Key Distribution Services
- o Facility Engineering
- o Central Office of Record
- o Logistics Planning and Support
- o Depot Operations
- o Technical Training

GSA'S APPROACH

GSA's service offerings, set forth above, provide critical NSEP users with a variety of inherent NSEP end-to-end services and features, as well as optional offerings, including better control of restoration and provisioning capabilities, thereby enhancing the Government's overall NSEP posture.

GSA intends to pursue a course of action toward which we continue to strive to incorporate future technology and service opportunities into our offerings to meet Federal user mission requirements.

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